

This code was used to produce Fig. 4b

The details can be found in the Methods section of *Mehl. et al. 2024*

$$\tau = \frac{1}{\omega} \left(\frac{\Delta}{g} \right)$$

$$[c] = K_d \frac{F_b}{1 - F_b}$$

```
s0 = 0.98;
g0 = 0.15;
% COMPUTE_CONCENTRATION computes the dye concentration from the user defined
%fraction bound matrix and a kd scalar, also provided by the user

%[g_projection, s_projection] = phasor_projection(handles);

%g_projection = 0.92;
%s_projection = 0.25;
n_sample = 10000;
concentrations_all = zeros(n_sample, 1);

g_projection = 0.81;
s_projection = 0.35;

g2 = 0.875; %handles.Comp1_G; % free
s2 = 0.285; %handles.Comp1_S;
g1 = 0.748; %handles.Comp2_G; % bound
s1 = 0.42; %handles.Comp2_S;

g1_dist = g1 + normrnd(0, 0.01, [n_sample, 1]);
g2_dist = g2 + normrnd(0, 0.01, [n_sample, 1]);
kd = 186; % nM

for i = 1 : n_sample
    g1 = g1_dist(i);
    g2 = g2_dist(i);

    c = 0.11;%ratio of free to bound brightness
    pb_p = sqrt((g1 - g_projection).^2 + (s1 - s_projection).^2); % vector phasor bound minus
phasor
    pf_p = sqrt((g2 - g_projection).^2 + (s2 - s_projection).^2); % vector phasor free minus
phasor

    FB = c*(pf_p./pb_p)./(1 + (c*pf_p./pb_p)); % fraction of bound biosensor
    ind = 0:.1:.9;
    tags = c*(ind./(1-ind))./(1 + c*(ind./(1-ind)));

    concentration = kd*(FB./(1-FB));

    concentrations_all(i) = concentration;
```

```
end
```

```
% tags = kd *(tags./(1-tags));  
% tags = floor(tags *1000)/1000;  
% interval = [.1*kd/(kd + .1*kd),10*kd/(kd + 10*kd)];  
% interval = (interval./((1-interval)*c))./(1+interval./((1-interval)*c));  
% interval = floor((interval)*1000)/1000;  
figure;  
h_hist = histogram(concentrations_all, 32, 'Normalization','probability', 'FaceColor','none');  
hh = gca;  
hh.FontSize = 18;  
hh.LineWidth = 2.0;  
hh.Box = 'off';  
xlabel('Concentration (nM)');  
ylabel('Probability');
```



```
pd = fitdist(h_hist.Data, 'Normal');  
pd.mu
```

```
ans = 20.2046
```

```
pd.sigma
```

```
ans = 2.0756
```